

Pioneering AI in MLTC: Bridging Research and Practice

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The
Alan Turing
Institute

Swansea
University
Prifysgol
Abertawe

Population Data Science
Gwyddor Data Poblogaeth

Focussing on the future:

How do we ensure impact through translation of your research to improve health & social care for MLTC patients, in the next 5 years?

The workshop logistics

The workshop was designed to provide members of the AIM community with an opportunity to discuss key topics shaping the future of AI and MLTC research, aiming to improve lives for those living with or caring for people with Multiple Long-Term Conditions. In collaboration with NIHR, six discussion topics with guiding questions were prepared to explore challenges and potential solutions.

The event welcomed 80-100 registered attendees, with 12-16 participants engaging in discussions on each topic and eight joining online. A one-hour session included 50 minutes for discussion, focusing on capturing attendees' insights and identifying three key takeaways for feedback.

There were 7 topics discussed in the workshop, this summary includes the discussion and takeaway from the 1st topic.

- **Topic 1: How can we mobilise knowledge that has been generated by AIM?**
- **Topic 2: What are the strategies & good practices for engaging and sustaining patient communities?**
- **Topic 3: How can we champion early career researchers in MLTC research?**
- **Topic 4: What technical support is needed for the next stage of translation/impact?**
- **Topic 5: Who do we need to engage to ensure broad collaboration for translating research?**
- **Topic 6: How would we move towards system thinking and transdisciplinary research in MLTC?**
- **Topic 7: What are the strategies & good practices for engaging and sustaining patient communities?**

Topic 1: How can we mobilise knowledge that has been generated by AIM?

Chaired by: Anastasia Kichinga and Mario Moroso

Scribed by: Ellie Harvey

The key takeaways

- We need to preserve and share the outputs, methods, and best practices from the AIM projects as a basis for future interventions. There needs to be a unified approach - one website, one github, one book.
- We have good foundations, but implementing our AI in the real world needs significant further investment: Co-designing interventions with stakeholders, building tools, validating the algorithms, gaining trust and buy-in from the public, and then measuring behaviour change and health outcomes.
- PPI is critical to this journey. They make sure research is relevant, accessible, and transparent. No AI will be accepted in the real world without patient buy-in!

Recommendations for MLTC funders

1. Establish a funding stream for translation and implementation: Allocate specific funding for translating validated algorithms into real-world interventions. This should include resources for:
 - Stakeholder engagement and co-design
 - Interface development and testing
 - Real-world validation in GP practices
 - Public trust-building initiatives
 - Outcome measurement frameworks
2. Create a unified knowledge mobilisation framework: Fund the development and maintenance of a centralised knowledge-sharing infrastructure that includes:
 - A single, comprehensive website for all MLTC projects
 - A unified GitHub repository
 - Dedicated resources for maintaining and updating shared resources
 - Support for PPI involvement throughout the knowledge mobilisation process
 - Regular stakeholder events to facilitate knowledge exchange and implementation planning

Summary of all the discussion

- We need to reflect on how to Mobilise AIM Knowledge?
 - Foundations are good, but there have been challenges...
- Some of the outputs are just “building blocks” for future interventions. How do we capture the algorithms in a way we can share with future teams? *“We don’t want to lose what you have built!”*
- What do we need to preserve and share our foundation for MLTC Research going forward?
 - A shared website for all our projects
 - A GitHub for all the projects
 - HDRUK Gateway – Tag all the projects
 - An edited book - chapters contributed by the project PIs
 - Record best practice – Methods, and the story behind the numbers
 - Prioritise key messages
- *Could RSF build these tools/outputs? Perhaps these are lessons for an RSF in similar consortia in the future?*
- We need one UNIFIED foundation for lots of different houses
- Who is our key audience? There are many audiences for our work so far: Future researchers, funders, regulators, patients. We need to share things in a way they can access and understand.
- We also need to share what we have been doing in terms of intervention development (not just the code)
- Now we have these foundations we need another couple of £million to translate the algorithms into interventions!
- Timescales – How important is it to validate the data before we work out how to put it into practice? We can start working the algorithms into interventions in **parallel**. Mock up the interface/service and iterate the design while finalising the AI.
- We need:
 - Events which bring stakeholders together
 - To validate what we have developed in CPRD in a GP Practice.
 - To bring onboard stakeholders like EMIS
 - A conceptual framework or “theory of change”. How does change happen? What are the contextual factors that are going to affect its use and adoption in the real world? *We need to understand the best way to implement our work* – innovation in healthcare is notoriously difficult!
 - To build public trust in the idea the AI can be used as part of a risk assessment tool. Transparency is key.
 - To be able to communicate with the real world. Researchers can be elitist and make patients feel “blinded by science”

- To measure the outcome, which is not just uptake of the AI, but **behaviour change** and **better health outcomes**.
- PPI need to “travel with you”
- Challenges – getting in the way of good, effective, timely research
 - Even with the best algorithms in the world, if patients are dehumanised and don’t buy in it won’t change behaviour.
 - Need to consider the acceptability of public health messages. There is a delicate balance between fear and engagement when it comes to risk factors.
 - People don’t have traffic lights. They don’t fit into thresholds or numbers.
 - Open Science is ideological. Not just driven by industry (making money) and academics (protecting publications), but the governance of this sector. The reality is competitive, selfish, and ambitious.
 - Policy is a problem. Data stewardship, data governance, the cost of licences and not being able to use in-house computing. CPRD (data providers) have caused lots of problems and additional costs.
 - Fair Data – It was naïve to believe everyone was going to collaborate and do it for “patient benefit”. People do share, but only if they see it as “mutually beneficial”.
 - Some variables don’t exist in the data, some data isn’t linked.
 - Red tape, legal side, political factors mean the scope/capacity is limited in social care.